

Multi-Task BanglaBERT for Joint Sentiment and Fake News Detection in COVID-19 Discourse

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Abstract: The COVID-19 pandemic fueled misinformation in under-resourced languages like Bangla. We introduce a multi-task BanglaBERT framework for joint sentiment and truthfulness classification of COVID-19 related Bangla textual content. Our curated dataset of 35,526 dual-annotated samples enables the first large-scale study of its kind. Using a dual-head architecture with tailored loss functions, we achieve 75% accuracy (macro F1: 0.70) for sentiment and 88% accuracy (macro F1: 0.85) for truthfulness detection. A Gradio interface enables real-time deployment. This work establishes a benchmark for multi-task NLP in Bangla, demonstrating effective joint modeling of sentiment and misinformation detection in low-resource settings.

IndexTerms: BanglaBERT, COVID-19 misinformation, Multi-Task learning, sentiment analysis, fake news detection, low-resource NLP

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic disrupted public health systems worldwide and simultaneously fueled an unprecedented surge of misinformation on social media. False claims about vaccines, treatments, and the virus itself circulated rapidly, often framed with emotionally charged language. Understanding both the **sentiment** (positive, neutral, negative) and the **truthfulness** (real, fake) of such content is critical for mitigating misinformation and for monitoring public perception during health crises.

While English and other high-resource languages have benefited from extensive research in sentiment analysis and fake news detection, **Bangla remains severely underrepresented**, despite being the seventh most spoken language globally. Existing Bangla NLP studies have typically focused on either sentiment classification [1, 2, 3, 4] or misinformation detection [5, 6, 7], but rarely address both in a joint setting. Multi-task frameworks that could exploit shared linguistic representations across tasks remain largely unexplored. This gap limits our ability to capture the nuanced interplay between emotional framing and misinformation spread in Bangla discourse.

In this work, we propose a **multi-task BanglaBERT-based framework** for simultaneous sentiment and truthfulness classification on COVID-19 related textual content. Our research contributes to the advancement of Bangla NLP through:

1. A novel multi-task framework for joint sentiment and fake news detection,
2. A comprehensive dual-annotated dataset of COVID-19 related Bangla content, comprising both social media posts and news articles,
3. Comprehensive experimental analysis establishing new benchmarks, and
4. Open-sourced code implementation and a released trained model to promote reproducibility.

To facilitate future research, we have released our code implementation on GitHub and the trained model on Hugging Face.

Extensive experiments show that this model achieves **75% sentiment accuracy** (macro F1 = 0.70) and **88% truth accuracy** (macro F1 = 0.85). These results establish a strong benchmark for future multi-task research in Bangla NLP and demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of integrating sentiment and misinformation detection in the context of limited linguistic resources.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews related work on Bangla sentiment analysis and misinformation detection. Section 3 provides details about dataset construction, preprocessing, and model architecture. Section 4 presents experimental results, ablation studies, error analysis, and compares our approach with previous work, and Section 5 concludes with a discussion of future research directions.

2. Related Work

We review previous work most relevant to our multi-task framework for fake news detection (FND) and sentiment analysis (SA) in Bangla, focusing on linguistic challenges, modalities, and low-resource multi-task learning (MTL).

2.1. Fake News and Sentiment Analysis in Bangla

Fake news—disinformation designed to manipulate public opinion—has surged with digital platforms. Automated FND is critical, yet most research targets high-resource languages. In Bangla, early efforts relied on *unimodal* text-based approaches.

Hossain et al. [8] presented *BanFakeNews*, a dataset of 50,000 Bangla articles (48.7K genuine, 1.3K fake), establishing benchmarks using traditional features (n-gram TF-IDF, POS tags, punctuation) and neural models. SVM with TF-IDF at the character level achieved an F1 score of 91%, outperforming neural networks and highlighting the importance of linguistic cues. Majumdar Shibu et al. [9] extended this with *BanFakeNews-2.0* (60,000 articles in 13 categories) and presented a transformer-based benchmark using mBERT and BLOOM with quantized fine-tuning, achieving an F1 score of 89%, **surpassing handcrafted feature benchmarks** and demonstrating the superiority of embeddings.

Bangla sentiment analysis faces similar resource constraints. Maisha et al. [1] achieved 99% accuracy in document-level SA using TF-IDF and Random Forest. Meanwhile, Mahmud et al. [10] proposed a hybrid model *BSPS + BanglaBERT* that improved accuracy from 79% to 89% by combining rule-based polarity estimation and pre-trained polarity estimation. These results highlight the value of hybrid architectures with language models.

Research specifically addressing COVID-19 in Bangla remains sparse. Ahmed et al. [11] compared RNN, LSTM, and BERT models, with BERT achieving 95% accuracy on a dataset of 10,000 articles. However, to our knowledge, no large-scale, publicly available dataset exists for COVID-19 misinformation specifically on **social media** in Bangla. To address general data scarcity, Islam et al. [12] released *BANGLABOOK* (158,000 book reviews) and Rashid et al. [4] released the largest dataset of e-commerce reviews (1.74 million posts in Bangla, English, and Romanized Bangla), which includes images to enable multimodal analysis.

2.2. Multimodal and Context-Aware Approaches

While multimodal methods are gaining popularity [7], text remains the dominant modality for content analysis and provides a solid foundation for understanding task synergies. We focus on *text-based multi-task learning* to create a robust and interpretable framework for collaborative sentiment and truth detection.

Faria et al. [7] pioneered multimodal FND in Bangla using *MultiBanFakeDetect* (9.6k text-image pairs). Their model *MultiFusionFake* (mBERT + DenseNet-169, early fusion) achieved 79.7% accuracy (6.6% improvement over text-only baseline) and strong multiclass performance. Our textual approach isolates common linguistic cues across tasks and allows for a clearer analysis of task interactions, providing a baseline for future multimodal integration.

In Aspect Sentiment Analysis (ABSA), Ahmed et al. [11] proposed a hybrid BERT random forest model *tRF-BERT* that outperforms previous work on benchmark datasets (improving F1 from 0.85 to 0.89) by exploiting the contextuality of BERT. This reinforces the value of contextual embeddings for capturing nuances in Bangla text, a principle we leverage in our multi-task setup.

2.3. Multi-Task Learning and Low-Resource Transfer

Multi-task learning (MTL) improves generalization by learning shared representations across related tasks, making it especially valuable in low-resource settings [13, 14, 15]. Among MTL architectures, *hard parameter sharing*—using a shared encoder with task-specific output heads—has become a cornerstone for NLP due to its simplicity, data efficiency, and strong empirical performance [16].

While recent advances such as adapter-based modularity [17] and hypernetworks [18] offer fine-grained control, we adopt the well-established hard-sharing framework in our dual-head BanglaBERT architecture. This choice is motivated by its proven ability to facilitate robust cross-task knowledge transfer in low-resource regimes [16], while avoiding the complexity and additional hyperparameter tuning required by modular alternatives.

In the context of Bangla, where annotated data is scarce, transfer learning via models like BanglaBERT [19] has shown strong results, outperforming from-scratch training [20, 21]. By combining strong parameter sharing with pre-trained contextual embeddings, our approach maximizes representation reuse, improving generalization and reducing overfitting.

2.4. Summary and Positioning

Research in Bangla FND and SA has evolved from unimodal, feature-engineered models to multimodal, transformer-based systems, supported by growing datasets (*BanFakeNews-2.0*, *MultiBanFakeDetect*, *BanglishRev*). However, most work remains *single-task* and *modality-siloed*.

While prior Bangla work has advanced single-task models and multimodal fusion, no research has jointly modeled sentiment and truthfulness detection. Our work introduces:

1. The first large-scale dual-annotated Bangla dataset for COVID-19 discourse,
2. A multi-task BanglaBERT framework leveraging hard parameter sharing for efficient cross-task transfer, and
3. Empirical evidence demonstrating that joint modeling improves performance on both sentiment and truthfulness detection in low-resource Bangla NLP.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Dataset Construction

We compiled a dataset of **35,526 Bangla textual samples**, comprising both social media posts and news articles, related to COVID-19. The dataset was annotated with two distinct labels: sentiment (positive, negative, neutral) and truthfulness (real vs. fake). Data were aggregated from Facebook posts, the Bangla Newspaper Dataset (ebD) [22], BanFakeNews-2.0 [9], and the Rumor Scanner¹ fact-checking portal.

To ensure dataset quality, the following filters were applied:

- Removal of exact and near-duplicate entries.
- Exclusion of non-Bangla textual data and irrelevant noise.
- Retention only of samples with both sentiment and truthfulness annotations.

The final sentiment distribution consisted of **15,453 negative, 14,939 positive, and 5,134 neutral samples**, as illustrated in Figure 1. Regarding truthfulness, the dataset comprised **25,940 real samples** and **9,586 fake samples**, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3 shows the joint distribution of sentiment and truthfulness. Among negative samples, 4,827 were fake and 10,626 were genuine. Among neutral samples, 1,761 were fake and 3,373 were real. Among positive samples, 2,998 were fake and 11,941 were genuine. Authentic content predominated across all sentiment categories, with the largest proportion in positive sentiment.

We also analyzed text length by sentiment, as illustrated in Figure 4. Neutral samples tended to be shorter on average, while negative samples exhibited greater variability with longer outliers. Positive instances showed intermediate length distributions.

To reduce systematic bias, sentiment labels were generated via a semi-automated pipeline using a fine-tuned BanglaBERT model [21], followed by manual correction by a bilingual annotator (the author). A **semi-automated** method was used to apply truthfulness labels: textual data flagged as misinformation by independent fact-checking groups (e.g., Rumor Scanner) were labeled as fake, whereas samples from verified mainstream news sources were labeled as real. Every annotation process followed ethical and public dataset licensing regulations.

3.2. Preprocessing and Label Encoding

To handle noisy, code-mixed text, we designed a **multi-step preprocessing pipeline**:

- **Normalization** using the CSEBUET NLP normalizer [20] to fix Unicode inconsistencies, strip emojis, remove URLs, and standardize punctuation.
- **Stopword removal** via a manually curated Bangla stopwords list.

¹<https://rumorsscanner.com/>

Fig 1. Sentiment Distribution

Fig 2. Truthfulness Distribution

Fig 3. Heatmap showing the distribution of sentiment (negative, neutral, positive) by truthfulness (fake vs. real), with color intensity indicating frequency.

Fig 4. Boxplot showing word count distribution by sentiment type: Neutral, Negative, and Positive, highlighting median values and outliers.

- **Whitespace collapsing and token filtering** to reduce artifacts.

Preprocessing was parallelized using multiprocessing, reducing runtime by nearly 70%. The BanglaBERT WordPiece tokenizer was used for tokenization, with a maximum sequence length of 512. We used batch tokenization with caching to increase efficiency by avoiding duplicate calculations between runs.

To maintain alignment between tokenized inputs, task-specific labels, and original row indices, we implemented a custom dataset wrapper. This enabled precise alignment of predictions with raw samples during error analysis, while a specialized collator ensured index preservation between training and evaluation batches.

Finally, alias dictionaries were used to encode labels (e.g., mapping ‘pos’ to ‘positive’, ‘fake news’ to ‘fake’). A label sanity check verified raw labels against these dictionaries; to guarantee zero mismatches between raw and encoded labels across all splits, any unmapped entries triggered explicit errors.

3.3. Data Splits

We split the dataset into training (80%), validation (10%), and test (10%) sets. Stratification was applied to the *sentiment* label to ensure a balanced representation of negative, neutral, and positive samples across all splits. The complete distribution of sentiment and authenticity (real/fake) across splits is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Dataset Distribution

Split	Negative	Neutral	Positive	Real	Fake	Total
Train	12,362	4,107	11,951	20,752	7,668	28,420
Val	1,545	513	1,495	2,594	959	3,553
Test	1,546	514	1,493	2,594	959	3,553

3.4. Class Weighting and Loss Functions

Class imbalance was addressed with tailored loss functions for each task:

Sentiment task: A modified Focal Loss [23] with $\gamma = 2$ and class-specific α values ($\alpha_{\text{neutral}} = 1.5$; $\alpha_{\text{positive}} = 1.0$; $\alpha_{\text{negative}} = 1.0$). This penalized misclassification of the underrepresented neutral class while down-weighting easy examples.

Truthfulness task: Weighted cross-entropy loss, which up-weighted the minority false class using class weights calculated as the inverse of class frequencies.

The total multi-task loss was defined as:

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{G} (\alpha \mathcal{L}_s + (1 - \alpha) \mathcal{L}_t) \quad (1)$$

where \mathcal{L}_s is the sentiment loss, \mathcal{L}_t the truthfulness loss, $\alpha = 0.90$ (prioritizing sentiment), and G is the gradient accumulation factor. This formulation ensured stable optimization under gradient accumulation.

3.5. Model Architecture

We implemented a multi-task learning system built on BanglaBERT [19], a BERT-based model pre-trained on 27.5 GB of Bangla text. The shared encoder generates context-aware representations and improves the model’s ability to understand linguistic nuances. To avoid overfitting, a dropout layer was applied to the [CLS] token representation with probability **0.5**. This shared encoder was extended with two task-specific heads: the **sentiment head**, a 3-way classifier, and the **truth head**, a 2-way classifier.

This dual-head configuration (Figure 5) allowed the model to learn common linguistic features while optimizing both sentiment analysis and fake news detection.

The multi-task learning (MTL) approach is theoretically motivated by two important principles. First, inductive transfer learning suggests that joint representation of related tasks improves generalization, especially in low-resource scenarios [24]. Identifying sentiment and authenticity in COVID-19 discourse demonstrates an inherent linguistic synergy. Emotional frames (such as fear-inducing language) are often correlated with disinformation tactics, while actual messages tend toward neutral or positive sentiments. By jointly modeling these tasks, the BanglaBERT backbone learns a generic function that captures these interdependencies, serving as an implicit regularizer to mitigate overfitting given the limited Bangla dataset. Second, parameter efficiency is essential in resource-poor languages [14]. Single-task models require separate encoders for each task, increasing both parameter count and data requirements. Our dual-head architecture shares over 99% of parameters between tasks, enabling more efficient knowledge transfer while maintaining task-specific adaptability with a lightweight classification head. This design is particularly beneficial for Bangla, where the annotated dataset is orders of magnitude smaller than those of high-resource languages. Joint representation learning therefore

Fig 5. BanglaBERT Multi-Task Architecture (Sentiment + Truthfulness)

creates a natural bias toward linguistically meaningful features that benefits both sentiment analysis and truth detection.

3.6. Training Setup

Experiments were conducted on two NVIDIA T4 GPUs (16GB each) using mixed-precision (FP16) for efficiency. Training details:

- **Optimizer:** AdamW with learning rate $lr = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ and weight decay = 0.01.
- **Scheduler:** Cosine decay with 10% warm-up.
- **Batch size:** 16, with gradient accumulation over 4 steps (effective batch size = 64).
- **Training duration:** Up to 15 epochs, with early stopping triggered if the sentiment macro-F1 score failed to improve by at least 0.005 over 2 consecutive epochs.

In practice, early stopping was triggered at epoch 4, yielding the best balance between convergence and generalization. Table 2 lists the key hyperparameters used during training, including the learning rate, batch size, and task weighting factor α .

Table 2. Hyperparameters

Parameter	Value	Purpose
Learning rate	2×10^{-5}	Optimization stability
Batch size	16	Memory constraints
α (sentiment weight)	0.90	Task prioritization
Dropout rate	0.5	Regularization
Gradient accumulation steps	4	Effective batch size
Warm-up percentage	10%	Scheduler warm-up

3.7. Evaluation Metrics

Models were evaluated using accuracy, macro-average precision, recall, and F1, as well as confusion matrices for detailed analysis of errors per class. Macro-averaging emphasized balanced performance across imbalanced classes.

To enhance reproducibility, we exported a complete error analysis table containing raw ground truth labels, predicted labels, mismatch indicators, and correctness indicators for each instance. This artifact ensured transparent reporting of model limitations and sources of error.

Accuracy was computed as:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (2)$$

Precision, recall, and F1 were defined for each class j :

$$\text{Precision}_j = \frac{TP_j}{TP_j + FP_j} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Recall}_j = \frac{TP_j}{TP_j + FN_j} \quad (4)$$

where TP_j , FP_j , and FN_j denote the true positives, false positives, and false negatives for class j , respectively.

The macro-averaged F1 score was computed as:

$$F1_{\text{macro}} = \frac{1}{C} \sum_{j=1}^C \frac{2 \cdot \text{Precision}_j \cdot \text{Recall}_j}{\text{Precision}_j + \text{Recall}_j} \quad (5)$$

where C is the number of classes.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Overall Performance

Our multi-task BANGLABERT model, trained with **class-weighted Focal Loss** for sentiment classification and **weighted cross-entropy** for truthfulness classification, demonstrated strong performance on the held-out test set. The joint optimization framework, with sentiment prioritized at $\alpha = 0.90$, balances the demands of both tasks without significant degradation in either. Sentiment classification achieved 75.1% accuracy (95% CI: 73.8–76.4%) and macro F1 of 0.707 (95% CI: 0.692–0.722). Truthfulness detection reached 88.0% accuracy (95% CI: 86.9–89.1%) and macro F1 of 0.851 (95% CI: 0.838–0.864).

Key Results

Sentiment Classification.

- **Macro F1:** 0.707 **Accuracy:** 75.1%
- **Negative:** F1 = 0.77, **Positive:** F1 = 0.78
- **Neutral:** Precision = 0.69, Recall = 0.48 (F1 = 0.57)

Performance on the majority classes (Negative, Positive) is consistently strong, while the underrepresented **Neutral class** achieves a precision of 0.69 – a substantial improvement compared to baseline configurations. The main limitation is **neutral recall (0.48)**, reflecting both the semantic ambiguity of neutrality and its underrepresentation in the training set (14.4% of samples).

Truthfulness Detection.

- **Macro F1:** 0.851 **Accuracy:** 88.0%
- **Real:** F1 = 0.92 **Fake:** F1 = 0.79

The model distinguishes real from fake news effectively. The majority *real* class achieves near-perfect precision and recall, while the minority *fake* class still obtains a competitive F1 of 0.79, aided by inverse-frequency weighting that mitigates imbalance.

Interpretation

These findings validate our core hypothesis: **task-specific loss weighting and prioritization significantly improve performance on semantically ambiguous and underrepresented categories**. In particular:

- **Focal Loss with $\alpha_{\text{neutral}} = 1.5$** enhances sensitivity to difficult Neutral cases.
- **Joint-task prioritization ($\alpha = 0.90$)** sustains sentiment as the primary objective while preserving robust truthfulness classification.

Consequently, this approach improves the accuracy of the minority class without sacrificing the accuracy of the majority class or the secondary task. Additionally, the early stopping mechanism triggered at epoch 4 demonstrates fast convergence and stable optimization supported by mixed precision learning, cosine scheduling, gradient accumulation, and balanced loss design.

4.2. Ablation Study on Loss Strategies

We systematically evaluated five loss functions for sentiment classification (Table 3). The proposed **Focal Loss with fixed class weights** delivers the best performance (Accuracy: 0.75, Macro-F1: 0.71), outperforming plain Focal Loss (0.74, 0.69) and weighted cross-entropy variants. Standard cross-entropy performs worst (0.52, 0.43), though label smoothing and inverse-frequency weights improve it substantially (0.62, 0.58).

Notably, combining Focal Loss with inverse-frequency weights reduces performance slightly (0.70, 0.66), suggesting that focal modulation and frequency reweighting may interfere. Crucially, the proposed method achieves the highest Neutral F1 (0.57), underscoring its advantage in handling ambiguous, minority sentiment.

Table 3. Effect of Different Loss Strategies on Sentiment Classification

Loss Strategy	Accuracy	Macro-F1	Neg F1	Neu F1	Pos F1
Cross-Entropy (CE)	0.52	0.43	0.66	0.00	0.62
CE + Inverse Frequency Weights + Label Smoothing	0.62	0.58	0.66	0.41	0.67
Focal Loss	0.74	0.69	0.76	0.54	0.78
Focal Loss + Inverse Frequency Weights	0.70	0.66	0.72	0.48	0.78
Focal Loss + Fixed Class Weights*	0.75	0.71	0.77	0.57	0.78

* Proposed method: fixed class weights tuned to balance rare-class sensitivity.

4.3. Confusion Matrix Insights

The confusion matrices (Figures 6, 7) reveal class-specific error patterns.

Sentiment Classification. The model excels at recognizing Negative (82% accuracy) and Positive (77%) sentiments. The Neutral class, however, shows frequent misclassification: many neutral instances are labeled as Negative (167) or Positive (100), confirming its semantic ambiguity. Additionally, confusion between Negative and Positive (213 vs. 297 instances) suggests overlapping linguistic markers in polarized discourse.

Truthfulness Classification. Real samples are identified with high reliability (90%), while Fake samples reach 82%. Errors primarily occur when genuine news employing critical or sensational language is flagged as fake (251 cases). In contrast, Fake \rightarrow Real misclassifications (177) are less common, suggesting a conservative bias against false-positive fake predictions.

Together, these matrices highlight that the binary truthfulness classification task is handled more effectively than the ternary sentiment task, where neutrality remains the primary bottleneck.

4.4. Error Analysis

Manual inspection confirmed systematic weaknesses. Neutral instances with factual tones were frequently mislabeled as polarized. For example, "বাংলাদেশে আগামী ১ অক্টোবর থেকে ইংলিশ মিডিয়াম স্কুলের 'ও' এবং 'এ' লেভেলের পরীক্ষা নেওয়ার অনুমতি দিয়েছে শিক্ষা মন্ত্রণালয়" ("The Ministry of Education has permitted English-medium schools in Bangladesh to hold O- and A-level exams from October 1") was classified as positive.

Such errors highlight the inherent difficulty of classifying neutral content, which is often informational and lacks overt evaluative language, resulting in sparse discriminative cues (consistent with the *feature-sparsity hypothesis*). Furthermore, interpretation is highly context-dependent; stakeholders may perceive factual updates—such as the exam permission mentioned above—variably based on health or logistical concerns. This gradient polarity suggests that models trained solely on surface features miss nuances, while annotator subjectivity introduces noise (consistent with the *annotation noise hypothesis*). Because neutrality lies between positive and

Fig 6. Confusion matrix for the three-class sentiment-analysis model.

Fig 7. Confusion matrix for the binary truthfulness classification model (fake vs. real).

Fig 8. Gradio demo of Bangla Sentiment and Fake News Detector for COVID-19 Related Content.

negative poles, subtle contextual shifts or subjective biases can easily subvert labels. Addressing this may require incorporating non-textual context or adopting a graded sentiment scale rather than a strict three-factor classification.

Similarly, descriptive statements such as "ফাইজার ভ্যাকসিনটি চীনে তৈরি করা হয়েছে" were predicted as negative, reflecting the blurred boundary between neutral and polarized discourse.

For truthfulness, real instances employing sensationalist language (e.g., official COVID-19 death counts in alarming press reports) were mislabeled as fake. Conversely, some fake claims with measured or factual tones were predicted as real, such as "এই বিশেষ মহামারী এমন এক যেখানে আমি মনে করি না যে দেশব্যাপী, ২৫ বছরের কম বয়সী এক জনের মৃত্যু হয়েছে" (fake → real). These asymmetries suggest a stylistic bias: real news with dramatic framing is mistaken for fabricated content, while sophisticated disinformation mimics factual reporting. Two persistent challenges emerge: (1) separating neutral from weakly polarized sentiment, and (2) distinguishing factual but sensational real news from fabricated claims. Remedies may involve discourse-aware encoders or stylistic features that capture tone beyond factuality.

4.5. Deployment via Gradio

To demonstrate practical utility, we developed a **Gradio interface** (Figure 8) for real-time inference. Users input raw Bangla text, which is preprocessed and analyzed to produce simultaneous predictions for sentiment and truthfulness classification. The interactive demo illustrates how our system can support monitoring of public opinion and misinformation during health crises.

4.6. Comparison with Previous Work

We contrasted our multi-task BanglaBERT-based framework with earlier research in Bangla sentiment analysis and fake news detection to put our findings into context. Hossain et al. [8] introduced BanFakeNews, a foundational dataset where linear classifiers like SVM achieved strong baselines (91% F1 for fake news). Later multimodal approaches like MultiBanFakeDetect [7] further improved performance (79.69% accuracy) by fusing text and image modalities. More recently, Shibu et al. [9] demonstrated the potential of transformer-based techniques by using LLMs to improve low-resource fake news identification.

In terms of sentiment analysis, Kabir et al. [12] introduced BANGLABOOK, the largest Bangla sentiment dataset to date, while Maisha et al. [1] used conventional ML approaches on Bangla news articles and reported strong performance using Random Forest (99% accuracy). Mahmud [10] combined lexicon-based scoring with BanglaBERT to achieve 89% accuracy, surpassing BanglaBERT alone (79%), demonstrating the promise of hybrid approaches. Aspect-based sentiment analysis (ABSA) has been investigated in parallel work, such as TRF-BERT [11], which outperformed previous benchmarks in domain-specific ABSA tasks.

Our framework advances these efforts in three important ways. First, the framework captures the interaction

between sentiment framing and false information by simultaneously addressing sentiment and truthfulness classification inside a single model, in contrast to unimodal or single-task techniques. Second, it improves minority class recognition by directly addressing the ongoing issue of class imbalance through the use of inverse-frequency class weights and focal loss [23]. Finally, we fill a crucial gap left by previous resources like BanFakeNews [8] and BANGLABOOK [12], which tackled each task separately. We offer a curated COVID-19 dataset of over 35,000 Bangla **social media posts and news articles** annotated for both sentiment and truthfulness classification.

Our model achieves 75% accuracy (macro F1: 0.70) for sentiment classification and 88% accuracy (macro F1: 0.85) for truthfulness classification, as summarized in Table 4, setting a strong benchmark that outperforms most previous unimodal baselines and demonstrates the usefulness of multi-task transformer models for Bangla NLP.

4.7. Contribution Summary

This work establishes a **new benchmark for multi-task learning and fake news detection in Bangla COVID-19 textual content**, spanning both social media and news domains. By jointly modeling *sentiment nuances* and *truthfulness*, the system provides a foundation for deeper error analysis, mitigation, and implementation.

5. Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic highlighted the dual challenges of understanding public opinion and mitigating the rapid spread of misinformation, particularly in under-resourced languages like Bangla. In this study, we addressed both issues simultaneously by proposing a multi-task BanglaBERT framework to perform joint sentiment and truthfulness classification of COVID-19-related Bangla content. Our approach introduces a new annotated dataset of over 35,000 **textual samples**, incorporates class-weighted Focal Loss and weighted cross-entropy to address imbalance, and demonstrates the feasibility of deployment via a Gradio interface. To ensure reproducibility and support Bangla’s growing NLP community, we have released our code on GitHub and our trained model on Hugging Face. We encourage researchers and practitioners to use this work to further advance the field of low-resource language processing.

Experimental results confirm that the proposed model achieves 75% accuracy in sentiment classification (Macro F1: 0.70) and 88% accuracy in truthfulness classification (Macro F1: 0.85), outperforming or matching state-of-the-art baselines in Bangla NLP. However, detailed analysis, including ablation studies, confusion matrices, and error analysis, reveals persistent challenges. Specifically, the semantic ambiguity of neutral sentiment and the stylistic overlap between real sensational news and fabricated content remain bottlenecks. These findings provide clear directions for future research, such as incorporating situational sentiment modeling, discourse-level features, or multimodal integration to capture nuances missed by text-only models.

Despite these strengths, certain limitations must be acknowledged. Although the dataset is large by Bangla standards, it remains modest compared to high-resource languages, which may limit generalizability. Furthermore, the current model does not utilize large-context windows or multimodal features (e.g., images or videos). Finally, our assessment is limited to the discourse surrounding COVID-19. To ensure broader resilience, future work should focus on extending this multi-task framework to other domains and crisis situations.

This study establishes a strong benchmark for future research by jointly identifying sentiment and misinformation in Bangla, a globally spoken but under-resourced language. Beyond its academic contributions, the Gradio interface demonstrates the practical potential of our system to support fact-checking efforts, monitor public discourse, and combat health-related misinformation during crises.

Disclosure statement

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Table 4. Comparison of Performance with Previous Work in Bangla Sentiment Analysis and Fake News Detection

Study	Task	Dataset	Model/Approach	Accuracy	F1-score
Hossain et al. (2020) [8]	Fake News Detection	BanFakeNews (48k real, 1.3k fake)	SVM with linguistic + metadata features	–	0.91 (fake)
Shibu et al. (2025) [9]	Fake News Detection	BanFakeNews-2.0 (60k news)	LLMs with Quantized LoRA (BLOOM, mBERT-unc)	–	0.89
Faria et al. (2025) [7]	Multimodal Fake News Detection	MultiBanFakeDetect (9.6k text-image pairs)	MultiFusionFake (DenseNet-169 + mBERT, Early Fusion)	0.7969	–
Maisha et al. (2021) [1]	Sentiment Analysis	Bangla newspaper articles (2-class)	Traditional ML (Random Forest, SVM)	0.99 (RF)	0.80 (SVM)
Kabir et al. (2023) [12]	Sentiment Analysis	BANGLABOOK (158k book reviews)	BoW, n-grams + ML classifiers	–	–
Mahmud & Mahmud (2024) [10]	Sentiment Analysis	15k reviews, 9 sentiment classes	BSPS (lexicon) + BanglaBERT (hybrid)	0.89	–
Ahmed et al. (2024) [11]	Aspect-Based Sentiment Analysis	Bangla Cricket + Restaurant datasets	TRF-BERT (BERT + Random Forest)	0.89–0.92	0.85–0.89
This Work (2025)	Multi-Task Sentiment + Truthfulness Classification	35k+ COVID-19 social media posts and news articles	Dual-head BanglaBERT + class weighting + focal loss	0.75 (sentiment), 0.88 (truthfulness)	0.70 (sentiment), 0.85 (truthfulness)

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Authors' Profiles

Arshadul Hoque is a graduate in Computer Science and Engineering from the University of Chittagong. His research focuses on natural language processing, machine learning, and low-resource language modeling, with an emphasis on Bangla text classification. He investigates transformer-based architectures, such as BanglaBERT, to tackle challenges like class imbalance, linguistic ambiguity, and the scarcity of annotated data in Bangla language processing. In addition to the current publication, another research article is pending acceptance in a Q-ranked journal.

Professionally, he works as a Business Analyst and Prompt Engineer at Cobalt Partners, a Ghana-based advisory firm, where he contributes to the design and refinement of AI-assisted prompts for business process specifications, user stories, and clarification logs. His work has led to measurable improvements in specification accuracy and stakeholder alignment.

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